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Exploratory Data Analysis Methods for TSX Mining Companies

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Abstract

This article presents methods for exploratory data analysis for all mining companies listed on the TSX Inc., focusing on data from a specific day, December 17, 2025, when the total market capitalization exceeded \$1 trillion. The methods in this paper can be extended from cross-sectional data to longitudinal data, enabling tracking of market capitalization over decades of daily data. This paper shows different combinations of data, including market capitalization, stock trading value, the ratio of trading value to market cap, and the age of the listing. The paper also shows some logarithmic transformations of different data series to highlight statistical features related to extreme values.

Keywords: Statistics, Time Series, Methods, Toronto Stock Exchange, Mining, Trading, Market Capitalization, Finance, Canada, Exploratory Data Analysis, 2025

JEL Codes:

A19 - Other	G2 - Financial Institutions and Services
B59 - Other (120)	G23 - Non-bank Financial Institutions
C0 - General	G29 - Other
C02 - Mathematical Methods	K2 - Regulation and Business Law
C14 - Nonparametric Methods	K23 - Regulated Industries
C15 - Statistical Simulation Methods	L2 - Firm Objectives, Organization,
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C4 - Econometric and Statistical Methods	L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products
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G0 - General	
G1 - General Financial Markets	
G19 - Other	
G17 - Financial Forecasting and Simulation	

Exploratory Data Analysis Methods for TSX Mining Companies

This article presents methods for exploratory data analysis for all mining companies listed on the TSX Inc. (2026), focusing on data from a specific day, December 17, 2025, when the total market capitalization exceeded \$1 trillion. The methods in this paper can be extended from cross-sectional data to longitudinal data, enabling tracking of market capitalization over decades of daily data. This paper shows different combinations of data, including market capitalization, stock trading value, the ratio of trading value to market cap, and the age of the listing. The paper also shows some logarithmic transformations of different data series to highlight statistical features related to extreme values.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of market cap for all mining companies on the TSX. Figure 2 shows the log transform of market cap to help focus on the probability distribution of smaller companies, making it easier to analyze patterns among less dominant firms.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the age of the listing for all companies on the TSX. Figure 4 shows the distribution for the market cap of all companies, but both axes have log transforms. The log transform of market cap is meant to rescale the data for the very large companies, while the log transform of the frequency axes is meant to deal with the large number of companies with market cap around $\ln(20)$ or \$0.5 billion. Figure 5 shows the distribution of the ratio of the total trading volume on the exchange year-to-date versus the market cap for each company. This ratio reflects something like an activity ratio for each stock.

Figure 6 shows a scatterplot that ranks companies according to the age of the listing. The Figure shows the market capitalization on one side and the activity ratio on the other to check for relationships between how actively a stock trades versus the size of the company or age of the listing. Are the largest companies also the oldest ones? Are the oldest ones the most actively traded? Figure 7 shows another way to investigate these questions based on the raw data for market cap versus trading volumes, which both have extreme values. Figure 8 shows the log transformation of both market cap and trading volumes, which have a linear relationship. Figure 9 shows the log transform of market cap and the raw data for trading volumes, which shows the logarithmic relationship between the two data sets.

Figure 10 shows a linear relationship between the raw data for market cap and trading value, especially with extreme values. Figure 11 shows the log-transform data for market cap and trading value, which also has a linear relationship. The linear relationships in Figures 10 and 11 show different relationships between the data for small values versus extreme values. Figure 12 shows the market cap, trading value, and activity ratio for all companies ranked by the age of the listing. Figure 13 shows the relative size of each company compared with the total market cap of all companies.

Figure 1: Distribution of Market Capitalization for all TSX Companies

Figure 2: Log Scale of Market Capitalization for all TSX Companies

Figure 3: Distribution of Listing Age for all TSX Companies

Histogram of TSX Listing Age for All Companies

Figure 4: Distribution of Market Capitalization at Log Scale for all TSX Companies

Histogram of Market Cap (C\$) Log Scales

Figure 5: Trading Value / Market Capitalization Ratio for all TSX Companies

Histogram of Trading Value / Market Cap (All TSX Companies)

Figure 6: Age of Listing, Market Capitalization, and Trading Ratio for all TSX Companies

Figure 7: Comparison of Trading Value and Market Capitalization for all TSX Companies

Figure 8: Comparison of Trading Value and Market Capitalization Log Scale

Figure 9: Age of Listing, Trading Value, and Log Scale Market Capitalization

Figure 10: Trading Value versus Market Capitalization

Figure 11: Trading Value versus Market Capitalization on Log Scale

Total Trading Value (LHS) vs. Market Cap

Figure 12: Age of Listing, Market Cap, Trading Ratio for all TSX companies

Figure 13: Market Cap for all TSX companies

TSX Total Market Cap (C\$) 30-November-2025
 \$1,013,868,731,802 one trillion dollars

These different ways to visualize the cross-sectional data for mining companies on the “big board” of the Toronto Stock Exchange. This exchange is where larger mining companies are listed, whereas the Venture Exchange is for smaller companies. The methods of exploratory data analysis used here show that there are extreme values for all dimensions of the data, including market capitalization, trading value, and age of listing. This paper further shows how to use logarithmic transformations of various data series to identify linear or non-linear relationships. For example, the raw data for market capitalization has a relatively small number of companies with very large values, and it is difficult to show statistical relationships for smaller companies; however, the log transform of market capitalization makes it easier to see patterns among the smaller companies.

References

TSX Inc. (2026), “TSXV MM Issuers November 2025” <https://www.tsx.com/en/resource/101>